

GAS PERMEABILITY OF PARTIALLY SATURATED FABRICS

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Abstract

When using prepregs in a vacuum bag only process to manufacture composites, an important criterion is the ability to remove gases from the laminate. Partial impregnation schemes allow gases to be evacuated through the unsaturated cross-sections of the fabric; however, the presence of resin restricts the flow of gases and the time needed to evacuate gases from the laminate will depend on the degree of resin saturation. To determine the effect of resin saturation on the time needed to evacuate gases from the laminate, Gurit ST94 Single Sprint prepreg (consisting of a resin film laminated to a twill weave carbon fabric) was tested for gas permeability as the resin film was impregnated into the fabric to saturate it to different levels. The results reveal that the dual scale permeable nature of woven fabrics has a pronounced effect. Interstitial space between fiber tows has a higher permeability than the spaces within the fiber tows. For this reason the resin film impregnates this space first, and for the same reason, the gas permeability of the prepreg with the inter-tow space saturated with resin, reduces sharply.

1 Introduction

1.1 Process Description

A relatively new development in composites manufacturing is the adoption of prepregs in vacuum bag only processing. Traditionally, prepregs are fabrics or unidirectional fibers which are fully saturated with resin, and intended to be processed under a high consolidating pressure (several atmospheres). The pressure applied normal to the prepreg laminate compacts voids, as well as condenses moisture.

When processing prepregs in a vacuum bag, special considerations are made to reduce void

formation under the limitation of one atmosphere compaction pressure. Gases which become entrapped during layup are removed by partially saturating the fabric with resin. The regions without resin in the partially saturated prepreg serve as pathways for extracting gases when the laminate from the assembly of the prepreg layers is subjected to vacuum pressure.

To process a prepreg into a composite part, prepreg plies are laid-up onto a tooling surface and enveloped inside a vacuum bag. Once this assembly is prepared, the prepreg stack is subjected to vacuum pressure to remove the air and other volatiles from in between the layers as illustrated in Fig. 1a. Once the gas has been fully evacuated from the laminate, the assembly is placed in an oven to reduce the resin viscosity which makes it possible for the atmospheric pressure above the bag to distribute the resin within the prepreg into the interstitial space between the fibers (Illustrated in Fig. 1b).

Fig 1a. Schematic of gas evacuation from prepreg assembly. [14]

Fig 1b. Schematic of resin impregnation after the assembly is placed in an oven. [14]

A partially impregnated prepreg consisting of a resin film layered on a dry fabric was studied to determine its in-plane permeability to gas as a function of resin saturation in the fabric. Fig. 2 shows the configuration of this fabric with the fabric and resin in separate layers.

Fig 2a. Schematic of the cross-section of Gurit ST94 prepreg. The resin is in a film which is applied to one side of the fabric. [14]

Fig 2b. Image of the dry side of Gurit ST94-RC200T prepreg. Fiber tows are 2mm wide with 3,000 fibers/tow. [14]

Fig 2c. Image of the dry side of Gurit ST94-RC303T prepreg. Fiber tows are 6mm wide with 12,000 fibers/tow. [14]

Unimpregnated cross-sections of the fabric in a partially impregnated prepregs can serve as pathways for gas transport. How the distributed resin in the fabric affects the transport of gas is still an open question in the literature. By characterizing the resin pattern in the fabric and relating it to the time

needed to evacuate gases from the laminate one can develop a characterization method for gas permeability through partially impregnated fabrics.

This paper addresses how the distribution of resin in a partially impregnated prepreg will affect the time it takes to evacuate gases from a prepreg laminate. The objective is to investigate how different levels of resin saturation in the fabric affect the time needed to reduce the pressure in the void spaces to vacuum pressure. It is important to quantify the relationship between resin saturation and gas permeability because it will allow prepreg designs to be optimised for processing.

1.2 Background

Gas transport through porous media has been studied and applied to many fields of engineering – including petroleum engineering, soil science, and composites processing.

The ability for gases to transport and be evacuated through prepreg laminates has been identified as an important factor in reducing voids in composite parts [1]. Gas removal from prepreg laminates is inherently more difficult than dry fiber preforms because of the network of resin which has tendency to trap pockets of air. The notion of introducing a pore network to a prepreg for the purpose of removing gases is not new; however, has only recently gained popularity due to the ability to process prepregs using vacuum bag and oven only.

There are several test methods which have been developed for determining the permeability of a porous material to gases (including prepregs) [2-12]; many of which do so without the use of a flow meter. Because flow rates through porous materials are often extremely low, a flow meter can be a significant source of error. Instead, most methods (in various forms) calculate gas permeability by measuring the pressure change over time in a known volume where the only flow in or out of the volume is across some length of the porous material.

Permeability only depends on the pore structure of a material. When the permeating fluid is a gas and a resin or a liquid has occupied some of the pores, the gas must find a flow path around the blocked pores. This has been studied in soil science,

where ground water saturating the soil has an effect on the measured gas permeability [12]. In a prepreg the resin occupying the pores between the fibers can be considered immobile, simplifying the analysis to a single phase flow of gases. This study qualitatively explains how the measured permeability of a prepreg consisting of a woven fabric will change as different regions of the fabric (inter-tow and intra-tow space) become saturated with resin.

2 Approach

2.1 Experimental

Several test methods now exist for the purpose of determining the saturation of uncured resin in partially impregnated prepregs and how it changes during processing [13-17]. The method for characterizing resin impregnation used in this study was developed by the authors in previous work [13,14]. Although this technique lacks the ability to measure resin saturation through the thickness of the prepreg, the advantage is that resin flow can be seen in-situ and can easily be initiated by applying heat when the sample is under vacuum or halted by applying ice water. The ability to start and stop resin flow means that the same prepreg sample can be tested for gas permeability for several discrete increments in the level of resin impregnation.

To change the resin impregnation, the resin film (from Gurit ST94 prepreg) is pressed into the fabric – and through a clear acrylic table – the resin flow on the dry side of the fabric is observed. Images taken at the dry side of the prepreg demonstrate how the pattern of resin flow changes as resin progressively occupies the inter-tow and intra-tow empty spaces between the fibers. The degree of resin impregnation is quantified by measuring the relative area shown to be saturated with resin.

Fig. 3 illustrates the experimental setup used to change the level of resin impregnation in the prepreg. The prepreg is placed on a clear acrylic table with the dry side of the prepreg facing down. Tacky tape is placed around the sample and a vacuum bag is sealed over it. A vacuum line is sealed inside the bag at one end of the sample and at the opposite end a tube connected to a pressure transducer is sealed inside the bag. Below the table is a CCD camera which records images of the

(initially) dry side of the prepreg at the table surface. To infuse the resin film into the prepreg vacuum is applied to the sample. Once the pressure transducer at the opposite end reads the same value as the applied vacuum pressure, then an IR lamp is placed over the sample to heat the resin. The heat reduces the viscosity of the resin, allowing the atmospheric pressure over the bag to push the resin film into the fabric.

Fig 3. Schematic of the experimental setup in which the IR camera is used to heat the resin and change the saturation level before measuring the pressure decay due to the vacuum at the other end.

Figs. 4a & 4b show the images of the resin saturation captured with the CCD camera. Resin is first observed to flow through the pin holes at the intersection of fiber tows, where there is a direct and unobstructed path for resin to flow downward to the table surface. Along the table surface, resin proceeds to fill the inter-fiber tow space. Once the large empty inter-tow spaces are filled with resin, the resin will then impregnate the fiber tows.

After some short time, when the resin film has begun to redistributed into the fabric to create a new state of resin impregnation, the IR lamp is removed from over top of the sample and a bag of ice water is placed in contact with the sample to immediately arrest the flow of resin and maintain the prepreg in a fixed state of resin impregnation.

Fig 4a. Images of ST94-RC200T prepreg showing various stages of resin impregnation as captured by the CCD camera. [14]

Fig 4b. Images of ST94-RC303T prepreg showing various stages of resin impregnation as captured by the CCD camera. [14]

Once the desired increased state of resin impregnation is reached, the prepreg is tested to determine its permeability to gases in that fixed state. The experimental approach for determining in-plane gas permeability is adopted and modified from our previous work [2]. The test procedure starts with atmospheric pressure in the vacuum bag. The vacuum pump is then started (at $t=0$) and the air pressure decay at the pressure transducer is recorded as air is evacuated through the laminate. The

pressure decay over time at the pressure transducer is compared to the model results (discussed in the next section) to determine the gas permeability. In accordance with the model, the length and cross-sectional area of the prepreg, as well as the volume of the tube at the pressure transducer are measured. Once the test is complete, the vacuum line is opened to the atmosphere and air is allowed to slowly refill the porous space in the prepreg – preparing the sample for the next gas permeability test.

Fig 5. Schematic of the experimental set-up in which vacuum is applied at one end to evacuate the mold and decay in the pressure is measured at the other end. [2]

2.2 Theoretical

The objective of the model is to find a theoretical curve for the pressure decay over time as measured by the pressure transducer at the other end as air is vacuumed out of the prepreg assembly. With the only unknown of the system being permeability value, the experimental curve can be scaled to match the theoretical curve and the scaling constant provides the prepreg permeability.

The gas transport inside the prepreg is modelled by satisfying the conservation of mass equation for compressible flows (Eq. 1).

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\rho u) = 0 \quad (1)$$

The density of the gas can be expressed with the ideal gas law equation of state (Eq. 2). In Eq. 2, $C \equiv R/M$ where R is the ideal gas constant and M is the effective molar mass of air.

$$\rho = \frac{P}{CT} \quad (2)$$

Darcy's Law for flows through porous media in Eq. 3 is used to express the flow velocity of gas through the prepreg, where K is the permeability, μ is the kinematic viscosity of air, and ϕ is the porous volume fraction. The use of Darcy's Law requires that inertial terms be small compared to viscous terms - i.e. low Reynolds number ($Re \approx O(1)$). For one dimensional flows, this is equal to

$$u = -\frac{K}{\phi\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \quad (3)$$

Density and velocity vary spatially and temporally but temperature variations are assumed to be negligible and permeability is taken to be an intrinsic parameter of the state of the resin saturation in the prepreg. When substituting Eqns. 2 & 3 into Eq. 1 the PDE in Eq. 4 emerges as the governing equation for the spatial and temporal pressure distribution in the prepreg

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = \frac{K}{\phi\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(P \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \right) \quad (4)$$

To model the experiment, Eq. 4 should be solved with the appropriate initial and boundary conditions. Initially (at $t = 0$), the pressure is $P = P_{atm}$ everywhere in the domain. At one end of the prepreg ($x = 0$) a vacuum pump applies vacuum pressure to the sample (Eq. 5). Hence the boundary condition at that end becomes

$$P|_{x=0} = P_{vac} \quad (5)$$

At the opposite end of the sample – some distance $x = L$ from the vacuum port – a pressure transducer measures the pressure drop in the sample over time. At this end of the sample a boundary condition of $\partial P / \partial x = 0$ could be applied, indicating a zero velocity flux of gas through this boundary; however, the pressure transducer interfaces with a vacuum tube which has a non-zero volume which cannot be neglected. Instead, this region of the system is modeled as a reservoir with a finite volume and reservoir pressure associated with the whole volume (Eq. 6).

$$P|_{x=L} = P_R(t) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 7 Schematic of the gas flow model through the prepreg with associated boundary conditions.

To reconcile the pressure inside the reservoir volume at the pressure transducer, the mass flow rate out of this volume is written from the time derivative of the ideal gas law in Eq. 7.

$$\dot{m}(t) = \frac{\dot{P}_R(t) V_R}{CT} \quad (7)$$

Where P_R is the reservoir pressure and \dot{P}_R is the rate change of that pressure with time and V_R is the reservoir volume. Eq. 7 is equated to the mass flow rate into the prepreg in Eq. 8, which follows Darcy's Law.

$$\dot{m} = \rho A u = -\frac{1}{CT} P A \frac{K}{\phi\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \quad (8)$$

Where A is the cross-sectional area of the prepreg. The result is Eq. 9, a PDE governing the pressure at the boundary $x = L$.

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = -\frac{KA}{\phi\mu V_R} P \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \quad (9)$$

To simplify the analysis, a system of non-dimensionalization is introduced in Eq. 10.

$$\begin{aligned} t &= \hat{t} t_c \\ x &= \hat{x} L \\ P &= \hat{P} P_{atm} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Where L is the length of the prepreg, P_{atm} is atmospheric pressure which is the initial gas pressure in the prepreg, and t_c is an unknown characteristic time scale of the pressure decay. The limits on the dimensionless variables are $0 \leq \hat{t} < \infty$,

$0 \leq \hat{x} \leq 1$, and $0 \leq \hat{P} \leq 1$. Eq. 4 is then rewritten as Eq. 11.

$$\frac{\partial \hat{P}}{\partial \hat{t}} = \left\{ \frac{t_c K_g P_{atm}}{\phi \mu L^2} \right\} \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{x}} \left(\hat{P} \frac{\partial \hat{P}}{\partial \hat{x}} \right) \quad (11)$$

The coefficient on the RHS is equated to unity.

$$\frac{t_c K_g P_{atm}}{\phi \mu L^2} = 1 \quad (12)$$

The B.C. in Eq. 5 becomes

$$\hat{P}|_{\hat{x}=0} = \frac{P_{vac}}{P_{atm}} \geq 0 \quad (13)$$

and the B.C. in Eq. 9 (utilizing Eq. 12) becomes

$$\frac{\partial \hat{P}}{\partial \hat{t}} = -\frac{V_P}{V_R} \hat{P} \frac{\partial \hat{P}}{\partial \hat{x}} \quad (14)$$

Where V_P is the total volume of the prepreg. Eq. 14 can be rewritten as Eq. 15 where it can be seen that the reservoir pressure is related to the pressure gradient in the prepreg.

$$\frac{V_R}{\hat{P}_R} \frac{\partial \hat{P}_R}{\partial \hat{t}} = -V_P \frac{\partial \hat{P}}{\partial \hat{x}} \quad (15)$$

Eq. 11 is discretized using the finite difference method with a second order central difference approximation in position and explicit in time. The boundary condition at $x = 0$ is applied directly and the boundary condition at $x = L$ is discretized and solved implicitly in time. At each time step the pressure distribution across the domain is solved and plotted in Fig. 8 for $0 \leq \hat{t} \leq 10$. It is noted here that the pressure across the domain at a given time is highly non-linear; indicating that the compressibility of gas is an important factor. A 3-dimensional plot of solution for gas pressure as a function of position and time is assembled from the solution in Fig. 8 and presented in Fig. 9.

From Fig. 9 it can be directly seen how the model expects the pressure to decay at the pressure transducer. The model prediction of pressure at the pressure transducer ($x = L$) is shown in Fig. 10 in terms of the dimensionless parameters.

Fig. 8. The gas pressure is solved at each position in the domain at increasing time steps. [2]

Fig. 9. Three dimensional plot for decay in gas pressure as a function of position and time. [2]

Fig. 10. Dimensionless curve for pressure decay over time at the pressure transducer as gas is evacuated from the prepreg. [2]

The method for obtaining the prepreg gas permeability is to determine the characteristic time scale of the pressure decay by matching the data collected experimentally to the theoretical dimensionless curve in Fig. 10. To match the experimental data to Fig. 10 the pressure axis is scaled by atmospheric pressure and the time axis is scaled by a value which makes the experimental pressure decay curve consistent with the model curve. The value used to scale the time axis is the unknown characteristic time (t_c) described in Eq. 10. Once the t_c that matches the experimental curve with the curve in Figure 10 is established, the gas permeability can be determined from rearranging Eq. 12 as shown in Eq. 16.

$$K_g = \frac{\phi \mu L^2}{t_c P_{atm}} \quad (16)$$

From Eq. 16 it can be readily seen that the characteristic time to evacuate gases from the prepreg increases linearly with decreasing permeability but increases with the square of the length scale of the part. This means simply that doubling a part size will take 4 times as long to remove the gases. This paper seeks to investigate the change in a prepreg’s permeability to gases as resin saturation in the fabric is increased.

3 Results

Each prepreg sample was tested for gas permeability at incrementing stages of resin impregnation. The results of this study are shown in Fig. 11. As stated previously, two samples of 200T and 303T Gurit ST94 Single Sprint prepreg consisting of a single layer of twill weave carbon fabric with a resin film laminated to one side of the fabric were characterized. It is assumed that the resin film does not penetrate into the fabric in the prepreg’s initial state. After performing the experiment to find the gas permeability of the prepreg at the initial state, the resin film is then pressed into the fabric to different degrees. By viewing the prepreg from the opposite side (through an acrylic table) the degree of resin impregnation is articulated by measuring the relative area which is seen to be saturated with resin. Once the state of

resin saturation in the fabric is changed, the permeability of the prepreg to gases is measured.

Fig. 11. Gas permeability of each prepreg at different degrees of resin occupation in the fabric as shown in Fig. 4a&b

The permeability of each sample was measured with no impregnation, referred to in Fig. 11 as 0% area filled because none of the resin from the film is shown to penetrate to the opposite side of the fabric. For each data point the gas permeability was tested several times and the average was calculated to be $5 \times 10^{-13} \text{m}^2$ for all samples (both prepregs). In this configuration, the spaces in between tows in the prepreg are empty - allowing these channels to transport gases (schematically shown in Fig. 12).

Fig. 12. Schematic of the cross-section of the initial state of the prepreg with the resin film on top and no penetration of the resin into the fabric. (0% area filled). [14]

The next incremental stage of resin saturation shown in Fig. 4 is ~5% of the area on the dry side of the fabric covered with resin. In this state, the space between the tows in the prepreg begins to fill with resin, making these channels

unavailable to transport gases (schematically shown in Fig. 13). The result is a sharp decrease in the prepreg's overall permeability to gases. The measured prepreg permeability drops to $2 \times 10^{-13} \text{m}^2$ in the ST94-RC200T and $1 \times 10^{-13} \text{m}^2$ in the ST94-RC303T – a decrease in permeability by a factor of 4 to 5.

Fig. 13. Schematic of the cross-section of the prepreg depicting the occupation of inter-tow spaces of the fabric with the resin from the resin film (5-15% area filled). [14]

The sequence was iterated for each sample until ~50% of the area at the dry side of the fabric is filled with resin.

4 Discussion

A woven fabric is considered a dual scale porous medium because characteristic pore diameters between fibers within fiber tows are on the order of micrometers where the interstitial space between fiber tows is on the order of millimeters. The inter-tow regions have a higher permeability than the intra-tow regions because the characteristic pore diameter is larger [18-21]. Illustrated in Fig. 12, in the initial state (0% area filled) the resin film is entirely separated from the fabric; therefore the inter-tow spaces and intra-tow spaces are available to transport gases is parallel.

As the resin film is pressed into the prepreg, the flow pattern shown in Figs. 4a & 4b indicates that the more permeable inter-tow space in the fabric will fill before the intra-tow space. With the highly permeable inter-tow channels saturated with resin, gas is forced to transport through the remaining pathways in the unsaturated cross-section of fiber tows where the fabric is less permeable. This accounts for the largest decrease in permeability occurring at the initial stages of resin impregnation. As resin further impregnates the fabric, resin saturates the spaces between fibers within fiber-tows. In this state the prepreg is a single scale porous

medium with the permeability of the fiber tows being the only contributing factor to the prepreg's bulk permeability. After 20% of the area is filled the gas permeability continues to decrease because the porous volume fraction of the prepreg continues to decrease as resin saturation in the tows increases.

To calculate permeability in this study the porous volume fraction was defined to be $\phi \equiv 1 - V_f \approx 0.5$. A more rigorous study should correlate prepreg's permeability to gas directly to the porous volume fraction instead of % area filled. Furthermore, porous volume fraction should be defined as a function of fiber volume fraction and resin saturation which could be $\phi \equiv S(1 - V_f)$ where S is the fraction of the porous volume saturated with resin ($0 \leq S \leq 1$). Because of the extreme difficulty of finding the exact volume of the fabric to be saturated with resin, this study is offered as a simple alternative to approximate the saturation of resin in the fabric and gage its effect on a prepreg's permeability to gas.

The value of this study lies mostly in the processing of large parts with partially impregnated prepregs. The time needed to bring the part to the applied vacuum pressure increases with the square of the part size (largest distance from a vacuum port) and linearly with the prepreg's permeability. In order for a 0.2m length of Gurit ST94-RC303T prepreg (with a permeability of $5 \times 10^{-13} \text{m}^2$) to reach 1% of the applied vacuum, it will take 12 minutes. If the part size is increased to 1m (5 times larger) it will take 5 hours to reduce the pressure to the same vacuum pressure (25 times longer). If during layup, the resin film is forced into the interstitial space between fiber tows (or the prepreg is purchased with that configuration of resin), the gas permeability of the prepreg will be $1 \times 10^{-13} \text{m}^2$ and the degassing time for a 1m long part will take 25 hours (5 times longer).

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